

EV drivers' willingness to accept smart charging: Measuring preferences of potential adopters

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ABSTRACT

The increasing convergence of the mobility and electricity sectors creates many opportunities and challenges around electric vehicle (EV) charging. It is a large interest of the industry to gain EV drivers' consent for smart charging to facilitate the smooth integration of EVs into the electricity grid and maximize the miles driven on renewable power. This study assesses the preferences of potential adopters of smart charging solutions. Employing a choice experiment, this study measures the extent to which and under which conditions EV drivers are willing to adjust the charging location, duration, and charging mode. Based on a sample of 202 current and potential EV drivers, a total of 6'240 experimental decisions for different smart charging offers were analyzed. The results reveal crucial insights into the preference structure of current and potential EV drivers. Based on these findings, this study offers recommendations for providers of smart charging to win early adopters.

1. Introduction

The use of electric vehicles (EV), and therefore charging them, is on the rise. This trend is good news because transitioning to a low-carbon mobility system is one of the most important contributions to fighting climate change. Replacing gasoline cars with EVs is a core pillar of climate strategies for nearly all nations (IEA, 2020). The technology substitution ensures emission-free driving. Already when driven for a couple of thousand kilometers, EVs are more climate-friendly than their fossil-fuel counterparts: EVs have reached the point where their life-cycle carbon content is clearly lower than internal combustion engine cars, as long as the electricity mix is not more carbon-intense than that of modern natural combined cycle powerplants (Bauer et al., 2015; Cox et al., 2020). In addition, the total costs of owning an EV today are competitive with gasoline cars in comparable models (Cox et al., 2020). While sales data for EVs show a significant increase in the total stock of EVs on the road of 8.5 million in 2020 globally (BloombergNEF, 2020), future outlooks predict even more impressive developments. Scenarios forecast EVs will dominate car markets and highways in the coming decades (BloombergNEF, 2020; IEA, 2020). Simultaneously, the EV charging infrastructure has to co-evolve with the uptake of EV sales (Encarnação et al., 2018). In 2020, public EV charging stations worldwide reached 1.3 million (BloombergNEF, 2020). To respond to EV diffusion forecasts, the charging infrastructure must be further expanded to ensure sufficient and attractive charging options for EV drivers. Once achieved, this signals adequate availability of charging options, which is a relevant factor in EV purchase decisions (Cousse et al., 2020; Patt et al., 2019; Wolbertus et al., 2018).

However, developing an extensive charging infrastructure is not sufficient. Uncontrolled EV charging, where EV charging follows the daily movement pattern of drivers and instant charging happens, is expected to lead to severe challenges. As long as EV adoption is

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low, charging has a minor effect on the grid (Hardmann et al., (2018)). With growing EV adoption rates, however, cumulated demand peaks will increase. While the impact of EV charging on peak demand on the national level is expected to be relatively insignificant (Rüdisüli et al., 2019), the impact of EV charging on a local and regional level is expected to be considerable (IRENA, 2019; Muratori, 2018; Pagani et al., 2019). Muratori (2018) finds that with an EV share of 50 %, peak consumption could increase by 30.5 %. Uncontrolled charging would, therefore, lead to expensive grid expansions in this scenario. Beyond this, even when general EV adoption is low, high local peaks are expected due to clustering effects.

Consequently, the energy industry calls for the development and implementation of charging solutions that facilitate the integration of electric mobility into the grid and further increase the use of renewable energies for EV charging (IRENA, 2019). Solutions emerge around smart and solar charging (Hoarau and Perez, 2018; IRENA, 2019; Lund et al., 2015; Thompson and Perez, 2020; SolarPowerEurope., 2019). Smart charging and vehicle-to-everything (V2X) are overarching terms for dynamically managed charging processes for the benefit of the grid operator, the market, the uptake of renewable energies, and the EV owners themselves. Addressing the increasing demand for EV charging with foresight enjoys high market interest and enormous potential in three core domains. First, the smart charging of EVs can help avoid unnecessary grid impacts and expensive grid expansions (IRENA, 2019; Muratori, 2018; Thompson and Perez, 2020). Second, when EVs are charged with renewable energies, more renewable energies can be integrated into the grid (Kempton & Tomić, 2005; SolarPowerEurope, 2019; Sovacool et al., 2017). Third, smart EV charging can unlock a massive flexibility potential to be used to balance supply and demand the power system (IEA, 2020; Lund et al., 2015; Thompson & Perez, 2020).

Inevitably, customer adoption is a crucial success factor for implementing smart charging solutions. The existing knowledge about EV drivers' preferences for participating in smart charging solutions is limited (Gschwendtner et al., 2021; Sovacool et al., 2017; Sovacool et al., 2018). A more in-depth understanding of the conditions under which EV drivers are willing to participate in smart charging solutions is needed. To address this gap in research, I investigate the user acceptance of smart charging solutions and aim to answer the following research question:

To what extent are EV drivers willing to adjust the charging location, duration, and charging mode to enable smart charging?
Specific insights are provided for the following two sub-research questions:

- i. Which consumer segments are crucial to consider when designing smart charging solutions?
- ii. Which compensation should operators offer to incentivize EV drivers to adopt smart charging?

Based on a choice experiment with a carefully crafted sample of current and potential EV adopters, this paper contributes to the broad literature on the social acceptance of electric mobility and flexibility innovations. First, I address the call to shed light on EV drivers' preferences to adopt smart charging solutions (Gschwendtner et al., 2021; Sovacool et al., 2017; Sovacool et al., 2018). Second, the results provide insights into how consumers evaluate trade-offs between different attributes of charging offers and determine their willingness to accept smart charging solutions. Third, by investigating concrete decision situations that EV drivers are likely to face, I offer hands-on insights into the design of smart charging offers. Fourth, I provide different pieces of empirical evidence to the literature on consumers' and prosumers' willingness to co-create flexibility (Kubli et al., 2018).

This paper is structured as follows. This introduction is followed by a discussion of likely situations for smart charging applications and a review of the relevant consumer science literature. In the third section, the chosen methodological approach is described. I then present and discuss the results of the study in section 4. In the conclusion, I summarize the key insights and provide recommendations for business developers.

2. Literature review

2.1. Vehicle-to-X and smart charging use cases

The terms 'smart charging' and 'vehicle-to-everything' (V2X) often serve as overarching terms for various use cases that intelligently control the charging and discharging process using information about the status of the grid, the generation of renewable energies, and user demand (García-Villalobos et al., 2014; Gschwendtner et al., 2021; Thompson & Perez, 2020). The most common concepts discussed under the umbrella of smart charging and V2X are controlled unidirectional EV charging sometimes also called vehicle-one-grid (V1G); vehicle-to-grid (V2G), which refers to bidirectional charging where electricity is also fed from the EV battery back to the grid; vehicle-to-home (V2H), which uses locally generated solar power to charge the EV; and vehicle-to-business (V2B), also called vehicle-to-building which is a sub form of V2H where solar charging happens at the EV owner's employer. CharIn (2020) provides a helpful overview on the fine grained definition of smart EV charging concepts. Implementing these concepts comes with different technical, regulatory, and social challenges (Gschwendtner et al., 2021; Thompson & Perez, 2020). While these concepts describe the targets of smart charging approaches, it seems helpful to think about the concrete situations when these concepts can be applied. The following four critical situations are examples particularly relevant for this study where a shift to a smart charging process is beneficial for the electricity grid and the increased use of locally generated solar power.

- **Moderate the home charging process with V1G:** EV drivers tend to charge their EV at home in the evening hours (Dorcec et al., 2019; Hardman et al., 2018). Smart charging, in this context, can manage the rising demand peak from EV charging, which would add up to the already high demand in the evening (Muratori, 2018) and spread it over the entire night, ensuring that the vehicle is fully charged in the morning.

Fig. 1. Conceptual categorization of vehicle-to-X concepts.

- **Solar charging at home with V2H:** EV drivers who own a rooftop solar PV plant can solar charge the EV, allowing self-consumption of solar power. A challenge for this concept is the often missing synchronicity between solar power generation and the times when EVs are plugged in at home (Hoarau & Perez, 2018). Nevertheless, the uptake of EVs can help mitigate the effects of increasing grid tariffs (Hoarau & Perez, 2019), which is often linked to the growing diffusion of rooftop solar PV (Kubli, 2018).
- **Switch to charging at work with V2B:** Alternatives to home charging will become relevant to attracting the early and late majority of EV adopters, compensating for the absence of private charging options (Patt et al., 2019). Attracting EV drivers to charge their EV at their workplace during the day is a promising option, which can also benefit grid operation. Ideally, charging at work is powered with solar power generated on the building, which has a more favorable fit between solar power generation and EV plug-in times (Hoarau & Perez, 2018). V2B charging can then be intelligently controlled so that EV charging does not lead to additional demand peaks. In this use case, particular attention needs to be given to when additional demand peaks arise from EV charging that coincide with situations when the company's load is already high, as this could lead to disproportional increases in the electricity bill when a capacity tariff is applied. Lastly, EV charging at work can also be offered as a fringe benefit to employees.
- **Provision of ancillary services with V2G and V1G:** Apart from providing mobility, EVs can also provide ancillary services to the electricity grid. Particularly, bidirectional charging that allows feeding electricity back into the grid from the EV battery can be used, among others, for bids on balancing power markets. These services are typically coordinated and offered by an aggregator. Although flexibility needs are present at the transmission and distribution system levels, a strong focus lies in existing trial projects that provide flexibility services to the transmission system operator (Gschwendtner et al., 2021). Providing ancillary services with the EV can offer additional income for the EV owner and enable a practical function of the EV when parked, similar to stationary batteries used in a battery swarm (Kubli & Canzi, 2021).

The four application concepts of V2X relevant for this study can be categorized along their level of grid integration and the integration of renewable energy (Fig. 1). The characterization along the grid integration follows the conceptualization by (CharIn, 2020). In contrast to (CharIn, 2020), V2H and V2B are here treated as separate application cases in light of the higher ability of V2B to integrate renewable energies (Hoarau & Perez, 2018). V2G clearly focusses on providing high levels of grid integration. Depending on the particular optimization focus and the local context, the extent to which V2G can contribute to integrating renewable energies varies heavily. For instance, solar-based electricity systems profit more from V2G than systems with high shares of wind power (IRENA, 2019).

2.2. Existing knowledge of consumer preferences for smart EV charging

The literature on consumer preferences for smart EV charging has been gradually growing in recent years, since the technological development of EVs and charging technologies has matured. The existing literature looks at the general public perception of smart charging and investigates concrete situations in which smart charging can be initiated. There are three main situations in which smart charging can be initiated: (i) at the EV purchase decision, (ii) through contracts, and (iii) at each charging event.

The findings regarding the **public's general perception** of smart charging are not particularly encouraging. Among mainstream consumers who have not had experiences with EVs so far nor have intentions to purchase an EV anytime soon, awareness of the concept of utility-controlled is generally lacking, and it is primarily perceived as confusing (Axsen et al., 2017). When the concepts are explained in more detail, mainstream consumers in Nordic countries expect that smart charging technologies could prevail in the

market, but also state that this is nothing they would like to engage with on a concrete level (Kester et al., 2019). Furthermore, mainstream consumers expect offers not to affect their daily routines and appropriate compensation for adverse effects so that they are willing to participate. In contrast to the two studies mentioned above, the awareness of V2G among actual EV drivers is considerably higher (Huang et al., 2021). In a concrete implementation, user-managed charging based on time-of-use tariffs is perceived as easier to understand but more challenging to use. In contrast, supplier-managed charging is perceived as challenging to understand but easy to use (Delmonte et al., 2020).

The first stream of literature investigating situations where smart charging can be initiated looks at **EV purchase decisions**. Most studies focus on the context of V2G with the option for EV drivers to generate additional revenue through bidirectional charging. A vehicle's general capability to perform bidirectional charging is rated as a benefit and relevant purchase attribute for a fraction of consumers (Chen et al., 2020; Noel et al., 2019; Parsons et al., 2014). The tested smart charging contracts include the following attributes: guaranteed minimum charging levels and obligations to make the vehicle available for a predefined amount of hours per month for cash payments rewarding the revenues from bidirectional charging (Parsons et al., 2014); or the share of the battery that may be used for V2G and the electricity mix used for charging for an initial allowance of the battery investment (Maeng et al., 2020). Respondents in Parsons et al.'s (2014) study saw a high convenience loss in the V2G contracts, and revenues are intensely discounted, calling for high up-front payments. Other results suggest that drivers are only willing to engage in V2G models once they can lend higher capacities of their EV battery (Maeng et al., 2020). Apart from the V2G domain, product bundles that add a solar PV plant and optionally a home battery storage (Priessner & Hampl, 2020) or a charging station (Plananska & Gamma, 2022) to the EV clearly increase the consumers' willingness to purchase an EV. New offers on the market also combine smart charging offers with leasing plans, such as LeasePlan in the Netherlands (LeasePlan, 2022).

A second stream of literature looks at **contracts** that include EV flexibility. Electricity contracts from utilities are the most frequently studied. Through electricity contracts, utilities can initiate utility-controlled charging to smoothen charging peaks and flexibility services. The tested contracts were defined through guaranteed minimum charging levels (Bailey & Axsen, 2015; Huang et al., 2021; Kubli et al., 2018), the minimum frequency the EV has to be plugged-in for smart charging services (Lee et al., 2020), the daily plug-in time (Huang et al., 2021), or the maximum number of interventions and prolongation of charging (Yilmaz et al., 2021). The three studies, Bailey & Axsen (2015), Kubli et al. (2018) and Lee et al. (2020), found similar levels of required compensation, despite different concreteness in their design.¹ Compared to other providers of residential flexibility, EV owners face lower costs of discomfort than heat pump owners and are nearly as low as PV-battery owners, making them an attractive target group for decentralized flexibility (Kubli et al., 2018). In addition, Yilmaz et al. (2021) find that contract elements that specify the drivers' right to override the controlled charging for a number of instances increase the willingness to participate in such models. The option of recharging with fast charging technology within five minutes also increases EV drivers' willingness to accept V2G contracts (Huang et al., 2021). However, it remains unclear how fast charging can be implemented economically in a residential context. Apart from contracts with utility companies, also contracts with electric mobility service companies and flexibility aggregators are plausible options (Poplavskaya & de Vries, 2020).

While the two previous options look for longer-term engagements with EV drivers, a third option to initiate smart charging is right in the **moment of charging**. In this situation, smart charging implications become concrete and tangible for the driver. Empirically, this third option to initiate smart charging is relatively uncharted terrain. Ma et al. (2022) investigate consumers' sensitivity to time-of-use charging prices for different time slots at home and public charging stations in China. The results show a high willingness to shift the charging time for moderate financial incentives.² Spencer et al. (2021) compare the results of six individual pilot projects with PHEV vehicles and some EVs. Their findings confirm that drivers do react to incentives aiming to (i) increase the number of plug-ins, (ii) shift the charging away from peak evening times, (iii) increase overnight charging, (iv and v) shift the charging to midday and times of solar overgeneration, and (vi) shift away from hours with high grid costs. Due to the stand-alone design of the pilot projects and arbitrarily chosen incentives, trade-offs between different incentives and sensitivity to different types and levels of incentives could not be evaluated.

Borrowing from studies that investigate charging preferences independent of smart charging approaches, the factors that influence EV drivers' charging decisions can be complemented. High preference heterogeneity exists among EV drivers for relevant attributes of charging options, such as the energy provided and the effective charging time (Daina et al., 2017; Ma et al., 2022). Charging profiles vary heavily according to user type and the location of the charging station (Pagani et al., 2019; Robinson et al., 2013). Based on a qualitative study, the location of the charging station is a relevant attribute for EV drivers to choose a smart charging option. EV drivers only consider smart charging options when the choice of charging station does not conflict with their planned mobility and no additional costs emerge (van Heuveln et al., 2021). EV drivers perceive price reductions for charging as more attractive than purchase discounts, annual bonuses, renewable charging, or priority access to bus lines (Geske & Schumann, 2018). When choosing EV charging

¹ In a Canadian sample, Bailey & Axsen (2015) find that individuals were willing to pay an average of 59 Canadian dollars (about 41 EUR) per year for an increase of 10 km in the guaranteed minimum charge in the nightly utility-controlled charging program, assuming a base charge of 84 km. Kubli et al. (2018) measure in a choice experiment the implicit costs of discomfort for EV drivers to provide different degrees of flexibility, finding a required premium of 3.9 to 45.2 Swiss francs per month depending on the applied model (3.7 to 43 EUR). In a Korean sample, Lee et al. (2020) find a monthly willingness-to-pay for participating in a V2G model of 9821 KRW (about 7.2 EUR), despite no factual information on the impacts of V2G service on the battery charging level of the EV.

² The results by Ma et al. (2022) show that a price increase of 0.7 CNY/kWh (0.097 euros/kWh) when charging at home and 2.2 CNY/kWh (about 0.31 euros/kWh) when charging at a public charging station should be sufficient to motivate EV drivers to charge at different times.

options away from home, [Wen et al. \(2016\)](#) find three main customer segments: price- and need-oriented chargers, chargers opting for every available opportunity, and EV drivers, who consider a more complex set of attributes for their charging choice.

Following the literature review, we can conclude that consumer preferences for smart charging solutions have received some attention in recent years. In particular, there has been a strong focus on the contract-based implementation of V2G. Surprisingly, other forms of smart charging have enjoyed less attention so far from consumer research, even though unidirectional charging approaches and solar charging face fewer technological and regulatory constraints for implementation today ([Gschwendtner et al., 2021](#)). Beyond this, several studies have responded to low EV penetration rates with samples that address the broad public. While these studies provide helpful insights into the attitudes of the general public and future mainstream customers, they do not necessarily reflect the preferences of actual and potential early adopters. Consequently, the practical relevance of these studies is limited, as respondents without EV experience and little or no knowledge about smart charging who asked for their preferences to choose a V2G contract, have low predictive power for early adopters. Notable exceptions are [Huang et al. \(2021\)](#) with a sample consisting of 100 % EV drivers, [Delmonte et al. \(2020\)](#) with a sample of actual and potential adopters, and [Ma et al. \(2022\)](#), whose sample consists to a significant extent of actual EV and PHEV drivers, and only a few who have little knowledge about EVs. For developers and providers of smart charging solutions, the question of particular interest is what premium is required by actual and potential EV drivers to shift from their standard charging solution to a smart charging solution. In the next chapter, I outline the methodological approach to quantifying the preferences of current and potential EV drivers for smart charging.

3. Methods and data

This study applies a choice experiment approach to investigate current and potential EV drivers' preferences for smart charging offers. Choice experiments are excellent tools to measure consumers' preferences for products or services where revealed preferences cannot yet be measured due to a lack of market penetration ([Hensher et al., 2005](#)) and are useful in understanding preferences of future adopters. In mobility and energy research, choice experiments have frequently been applied to measure consumer preferences ([Huang et al., 2021](#); [Kubli et al., 2018](#); [Plananska & Gamma, 2022](#); [Priessner & Hampl, 2020](#); [Stoiber et al., 2019](#); [Wolbertus et al., 2018](#); [Yilmaz et al., 2021](#)). For this study, two particular methodological challenges must be addressed. First, smart charging concepts have repeatedly been reported as difficult for users to understand, and the concrete implications remained unclear for respondents. Second, the population likeliest to adopt smart charging offers are actual EV drivers. However, the penetration of EV drivers is still low, and stated preference analyses require decent sample sizes. To address the first challenge, this study puts the respondents in a concrete decision situation where they can choose whether to accept a smart charging solution or not. For this matter, a definite decision-making situation in daily life is described, sketching the impact of smart charging visually in a simplified form. To address the second challenge, the study uses a carefully crafted sample of current EV drivers and people who explicitly state that they intend to buy an EV within the following years. Further, in formulating the experimental design, the perspective of smart charging providers was considered to ensure that business relevant aspects are included. The early scoping phase of this research was supported by three interviews with practitioners active in the field of smart EV charging. The interviewees highlighted the relevance of the location, duration and day time of the charging process for the grid impact. The location and charging duration have later been implemented as attributes in the choice experiment.

3.1. Methodological approach

For this study, I conducted a web-based choice experiment using the choice-based conjoint analysis approach. The method is particularly suited for situations where decisions are formed based on multi-attribute settings, and trade-offs play an essential role in decision formation. In choice experiments, the choice situation is designed as a task in which one option has to be chosen over alternative options. Choice options are characterized by attributes and expressions of these attributes, called levels. Respondents complete a set of choice tasks, each comprised of choice options with different constellations of attribute levels.

The choice-based conjoint analysis builds on utility maximization theory. Respondents are assumed to make decisions that maximize their individual utility, for which the sum of the partial characteristics of the options is evaluated. Mathematically expressed, the utility of a decision option U_d is defined as the sum of the part-worth utilities $u_{i,j}$ that are evaluated for all attribute levels i, j .

$$U_d = \sum_{i,j=n} u_{i,j} \quad (1)$$

Hierarchical-Bayes (HB) estimation is used to determine the part-worth utility values from individual decisions, commonly chosen as the estimation method for choice experiments ([Orme, 2000](#)). HB estimations builds on two levels – an upper population level and a lower or individual level. The HB algorithm borrows missing information on the individual level from the overall sample of respondents ([Sawtooth, 2016](#)). This approach leads to more precise coefficient estimates than standard estimation procedures, especially in the case of preference heterogeneity ([Lenk et al., 1996](#); [Wuebker et al., 2015](#)).

A root-likelihood parameter (RHL) can be used as an indicator for the model's goodness of fit ([Sawtooth, 2016](#)). The RHL parameter has a maximum of 1, representing a perfect model fit to all individual choices. The presented model results exhibit a RHL value of 0.61. Three options were presented in each choice task, consequently the null likelihood is $1/3 = 0.333$ ([Sawtooth, 2016](#)). The RHL value is therefore 1.83 times better than the null likelihood.

To determine the premium required to incentivize EV drivers to change to an alternative charging option, the willingness-to-accept

Table 1

Design of the choice experiment for charging options along four attributes with three levels each.

Attributes	Levels		
Location	At home	At work	At a public charging station
Costs	0 CHF	10 CHF	20 CHF
Duration	2 h	4 h	6 h
Guaranteed range after 50 % of the charging duration	5 %	50 %	95 %
	ECO mode	Standard mode	Comfort mode

(WTA) calculation was adopted. Note that changes to alternative charging options can result in positive and negative WTA values. Negative values indicate that compensation from the provider is needed, whereas positive values show that the user pays less than the perceived individual utility. To calculate WTA, a standard charging model is assumed (i, ref), from which the EV driver is incentivized to shift away to an alternative (i, j). The WTA was calculated based on the difference between the reference level $u_{i,ref}$ and the target attribute level $u_{i,j}$ and the factor MC . MC is the linear monetary utility value for the attribute ‘charging costs’ (cc). It is calculated based on the difference between the maximum and minimum part-worth utility of the financial attribute ($u_{cc,max} - u_{cc,min}$) and the difference of the attribute levels ($CC_{max} - CC_{min}$).

$$WTA = \frac{u_{i,ref} - u_{i,j}}{MC} \quad (2)$$

$$MC = \frac{u_{cc,max} - u_{cc,min}}{CC_{max} - CC_{min}} \quad (3)$$

Latent class multinomial logit is used for the latent class analysis, as it is implemented in the Sawtooth software package (Sawtooth, 2021). The respondents preference structure is used as the input for the latent class analysis. The preferred model presented was selected based on several analysis iterations with different class numbers. The latent class analysis has been performed with two, three, four and five groups. The statistical criteria suggest the 3- and 5-group model. The BIC and CAIC values are the lowest for the 3-group model, whereas AIC and ABIC suggest the 5-group model as best option.³ The final decision for the preferred model was made based on an analysis of the effective groups characteristics resulting and their explanatory power. The 3-group model shows three clearly distinct segments that each have a preference structure that is also qualitatively different from the other groups. Adding two more groups could not provide fundamentally new insights of the same practical value.

3.2. Experimental design

In the effort to make smart charging concepts as approachable as possible, respondents are introduced to a specific, easy-to-understand situation that could emerge in their life as EV drivers. The following text was presented to the respondents⁴:

Imagine the following situation. You depart with your EV in the morning and realize that the battery of your EV needs to be charged in the course of the day. With the remaining range on your planned route, you can reach the following three charging stations. Each charging option increases the range of your EV by 120 km. At all charging options, you can use the time during charging with your planned activity (e.g., at the public charging station, visit a restaurant, shopping mall, sports event, or something similar). However, there are differences in terms of charging duration, costs, and charging mode. Which charging option do you choose?

The introductory text was formulated to control for three particularly relevant aspects. First, the situation was crafted to avoid interference with EV drivers’ potential range anxiety. Range anxiety can play a relevant role for EV drivers (Geske & Schumann, 2018; van Heuveln et al., 2021). However, this study focuses on the decision for smart charging options, and it is expected that modern smart charging offers will either generally avoid situations in which EV drivers are faced with insufficient range or provide users with opt-out or manual override options. Opt-out options have not only been found to clearly increase the willingness to participate in smart charging schemes (Yilmaz et al., 2021), in some cases EV drivers also considered it a necessary precondition (Hoekstra & Refa, 2017). For these reasons, range anxiety situations were eliminated through the experimental design. Second, the situation was designed to give light pressure to decide when and where to charge. At the same time, the impression of a high emergency is avoided. The consequently presented charging options all ensure a range increase of 120 km, which ensures that the next trips can be undertaken,

³ AIC = Akaike Info Criterion, CAIC = Consistent Akaike Info Criterion, BIC = Bayesian Information Criterion, ABIC = Adjusted Bayesian Info Criterion.

⁴ The original text was in German and French language and was translated for the purpose of this paper.

and the range addition is not unrealistic for older EV models. Third, following the qualitative statements from mainstream consumers that emphasize a low willingness to actively engage with smart charging daily (Kester et al., 2019), the experimental design foresees that all charging options can be combined with planned day activities. Therefore, the charging time can be used effectively.

The respondents were then presented with three charging options for each choice task. The experimental design was conceptualized in a choice-based conjoint format. Charging offers are characterized by four attributes, each having three levels (Table 1). The cornerstones of the charging offers are the four attributes: location, costs, duration, and the guaranteed range after 50 % of the charging duration.

While previous studies on smart charging considered the **charging location** fixed, this study tests the importance of the location of the charging offer. Based on the daily movement pattern of people, the time when charging stations will be used can be forecasted based on their location. Home charging typically happens in the evening hours, whereas charging at work is more commonly done during daytime hours. Today, 50–80 % of all charging events happen at home charging stations, while charging at work and public charging stations come in second and third, respectively (Hardman et al., 2018). With that, a time-of-day effect results in a charging pattern (Dorcec et al., 2019) that varies across locations (Pagani et al., 2019; Robinson et al., 2013). In addition, with the location of the charging station, potential combinations with the generation of renewable energies can be considered. In particular, solar charging at work has become an attractive option due to a good match between plug-in times and solar generation times (Hoarau & Perez, 2018). Public charging stations are expected to be the least preferred by users. Due to the higher usage frequency, these locations become interesting for high-capacity charging. For these reasons, the experimental design considers (i) at home, (ii) at work, and (iii) at a public charging station as levels for the attribute charging location.

Charging costs are a classical attribute in choice experiments investigating charging options. For this study, this attribute is particularly relevant to determining the premium to incentivize EV drivers to change charging options. The levels range from (i) 0 CHF, (ii) 10 CHF, and (iii) 20 CHF. The bandwidth of the costs was determined by analyzing charging costs in the country where the study was conducted. The level “0 CHF” is included for options where the flexibility value of smart charging can compensate for the charging costs.

The level expressions of the attribute **charging duration** match the bandwidth of likely charging options, ranging from low to medium capacity charging. Fast charging was not considered in this study. The levels used for charging duration were (i) two hours, (ii) four hours, and (iii) six hours. It is important to note that the attribute is called ‘charging duration’ to make it easy for the respondents to understand. From a technical perspective, the attribute ‘charging duration’ can be interpreted as the plug-in time. Charging speed as such was found to be of minor importance for EV drivers (Dorcec et al., 2019). Whereas, the plug-in time is relevant (Daina et al., 2017; Ma et al., 2022). From an operator’s perspective, longer plug-in times allow more options to shift or stretch the charging, allowing smart charging.

The attribute **guaranteed range after 50 % of the charging duration** captures the **charging mode**. This attribute translates the implications of smart charging from the EV drivers’ perspective, making it tangible for the respondents. At the same time, this approach assumes that details about the charging process are not specifically relevant to the respondents. What is relevant to them is the extent to which they give the charging provider degrees of freedom to co-create flexibility (following the analogy used in Kubli et al., (2018)). The levels of the charging mode attribute were complemented with a graphical illustration of what a likely development of the EV battery’s state of charge would look like. Three levels are implemented for the attribute ‘guaranteed range after 50 % of the charging duration’:

- (i) 5 % - ECO mode: This level gives maximum freedom to the smart charging operator, with the only conditions that after half of the charging duration, 5 % of the range has to be provided, and at the end of the charging duration, the promised range of 120 km has to be ensured (equal to 100 % in our example). In this mode, the charging process can be moderated to flatten or shift peaks. Charging can be synchronized with solar power generation, or bidirectional charging can be performed.
- (ii) 50 % - Standard mode: The second level is more moderate and comes closer to what EV drivers are used to from home charging. This mode leaves the operator degrees of freedom between the conditions that 50 % of the promised range has to be achieved after half of the charging duration and by the end of it, 100 %. This allows the operator to level the charging over the entire charging period. When the charging duration is extended or a higher charging capacity is installed, more advanced forms of smart charging can be performed.
- (iii) 95 % - Comfort mode: In this case, the EV driver enjoys complete priority charging. The EV is charged as fast as possible, and after half of the charging duration, 95 % has to be ensured. This constrains the charging operator and leaves almost no room to moderate the charging process. Technically, this is the process that is currently applied to all uncontrolled charging processes. Depending on the effective charging capacity and the charging duration, the battery state of charge after half of the charging duration can be nearly full or only medium charged.

Based on the choice experiment design described above, respondents were presented with nine choice tasks, each consisting of three charging offers with different constellations. The choice tasks were generated using full computerized randomization using a ‘balanced overlap’ approach, ensuring that the main effects as well as higher-order effects are measured well (Chrzan & Orme, 2000). Respondents were then asked to select their preferred charging option.

3.3. Sample

Following the research question, a sample consisting of current and potential adopters of EVs was targeted. The choice experiment

Fig. 2. Importance factors of the attributes characterizing the charging offers (n = 202).

was embedded in a more extensive study with a sample representative of the Swiss population (n = 1'021) (Cousse et al., 2020). The sample was recruited by a Swiss market research agency, using their panel of 110'000 Swiss consumers.⁵ The respondents were selected from the main sample using three screening criteria:

- People who own an EV or plug-in hybrid electric vehicle today
- People intending to buy a car within the next two years and consider an EV as their first or second choice
- People intending to buy a car within the next three to five years and consider an EV as their first or second choice

These criteria resulted in a sample size of 202 qualified respondents. From the overall Swiss representative sample (Cousse et al., 2020), the sample of actual and potential EV adopters represents a share of 19.7 %, indicating that EV diffusion can be significantly increased. Actual EV and PHEV owners make up 9 % of the sample, whereas the potential adopters intending to buy an EV within the next two years were 31 %, and the potential adopters to purchase an EV within the next three to five years were 60 %.⁶ The choice experiment was implemented in Sawtooth's software package Lighthouse Studio and conducted as an online survey. The survey was conducted in German and French, covering Switzerland's two largest language regions in early 2020.

4. Results and discussion

This section presents EV drivers' willingness to adjust relevant attributes of charging offers, based on the sample of current and potential EV adopters. Subsequently, I introduce the insights of the latent class analysis to gain an improved understanding of key customer segments. Delving into the practically relevant questions, the results from the willingness-to-accept analysis are discussed and applied to specific situations. Table 5 in the appendix provides a combined overview on the results that will here be introduced in step-wise manner.

4.1. EV drivers' willingness to adjust location, duration, and charging mode to enable smart charging

Fig. 2 shows the choice experiment results with the attributes' importance factor (Fig. 2).

The analysis of the relative attribute importance reveals that EV drivers put the highest weight on the charging costs when deciding on the charging options. Charging location follows charging costs as the second most important attribute. The two lowest importance factors are charging duration and charging mode. While costs outweigh all other attributes, the impact of providing flexibility (as captured in the attribute 'guaranteed range after 50 % of the charging duration', which was abbreviated as 'charging mode') is of considerably lower importance for potential adopters. This implies a low sensitivity of EV drivers toward a moderated charging process, as long as the EV is fully charged at the end of the charging duration. In addition, the location of charging station is relatively more important than the potential impact of smart charging, which is a good ground for developing smart charging offers. In combination with the high importance of the charging costs, financial compensation (in the form of a bonus or cost reduction) on the charging tariff can motivate EV drivers to participate in smart charging.

Fig. 3 displays the analysis of the attribute levels' part-worth utilities, revealing how EV drivers rate different characteristics of charging options.

⁵ <https://www.intervista.ch/>.

⁶ Respondents who owned an EV and were intending to buy another EV within the next 2 or 3–5 years were counted as owners only.

Fig. 3. Part-worth utilities for the attribute levels (n = 202).

Table 2

Latent analysis highlighting three key user segments and the class-specific attribute importance factors.

	Segment 1	Segment 2	Segment 3
Segment size	53.2 %	18.7 %	28.1 %
Location	23.92	28.55	26.77
Charging costs	51.34	10.68	31.45
Charging duration	13.75	13.70	14.13
Charging mode	10.99	47.07	27.64

The analysis of the part-worth utility curves highlights the wide spread of the attribute charging costs, reflecting its high importance. A free charging process enjoys a favorable attraction, leading to a slightly convex part-worth utility curve. There is a clear ranking of the options for charging locations, with home charging clearly preferred over the other options. Charging stations at work rank second, while public charging stations are the least preferred. The charging duration has a very linear part-worth utility curve between the options of two, four, and six hours of charging, where a shorter charging duration is preferred over a longer one. The part-worth utilities for the levels of the attribute charging mode reveal some interesting insights. The preference order of the levels is clear and follows what can be intuitively expected: comfort charging leading over standard and ECO charging. However, this preference order indicates an important aspect: Despite that EV drivers are guaranteed a fully charged battery by the end of the predefined charging duration, the processes occurring during charging still matter for EV drivers. A likely explanation is that EV drivers still anticipate that there is a chance they might depart earlier than planned. In contrast to the ECO charging mode, which has the highest perceived uncertainty, the standard and comfort charging modes are rated as relatively similar. Interestingly, the comfort charging option, which ensures that the battery is charged with full capacity from the beginning, is not perceived as a significant benefit and has only a slightly higher part-worth utility than the standard charging mode.

Following the part-worth utilities for the attribute levels, the empirical data confirm the expectation that the ideal charging constellation for an EV driver is to charge at home, for free, in the shortest time possible, with a comfort charging mode that ensures that the battery is charged up to 95 % after half of the charging duration. However, these insights vary across consumer segments.

4.2. Latent class analysis

The latent class analysis results are presented in Table 2, complemented with Fig. 4. The latent class analysis reveals different segments within the sample that should be considered for the marketing of smart charging solutions. The preferred analysis is three-group segmentation. The three groups can be distinguished by their weight on the different attributes of the charging options (Table 2) (see Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Part-worth utilities for the attribute charging mode for the three segments found in the latent class analysis.

Segment 1 includes half of the sample (53.2%). This segment is characterized by a very high emphasis on charging costs. All other attributes have lower importance, with the charging mode having the most negligible impact on their choice. Due to their high price sensitivity, members of this class can be good targets for smart EV charging with lower charging tariffs or other forms of financial incentives. Considering the size of this segment, these are likely to make up the early majority of the innovation diffusion smart EV charging offers.

Segment 2 places the highest importance on the attribute charging mode, thus outweighing all other attributes by far. The class-specific part-worth utilities reveal that the high importance originates from a substantial negative value for ECO charging (see Fig. 4). This group strictly avoids moderated charging, which involves deficient charging states during the charging process. Consequently, these EV drivers won't be suited for an advanced smart EV charging offer. However, the standard charging mode is already valued with a positive part-worth utility, leaving room for some moderation. Smart charging providers will be relieved to hear that this segment makes up 18.7% of the sample and not more.

Segment 3 shows a balanced weighting of the attributes; only the charging duration falls back. Interestingly and crucial, members of this segment prefer the ECO mode, resulting in a reversed part-worth utility curve for the charging mode attribute compared to the other two segments (Fig. 4). This preference implies that the members of this group actively seek to contribute to smart EV charging. Consequently, this segment can be targeted with smart charging offers early on, as this is the group with the highest potential for the early adoption of smart charging solutions. Providers should keep in mind that this group considers all attributes for their decision, despite their preference for the ECO charging mode. Consequently, offers should be carefully designed to consider all attributes. As compensation for the readiness to provide flexibility, forms of compensation other than pure financial payments can be considered. Members of this class are likely to adopt smart EV charging offers early on. Overall, the segment can contribute to a substantial mass, considering the relative class size of 28.1%. Latent class analysis with more classes indicates that the segment with this preference profile is robust and remains at a similar size (32.3% with four classes and 29.0% with five classes).

The findings confirm the relevance of segment-specific considerations when it comes to smart charging offers (Wen et al., 2016; Yilmaz et al., 2021). The found segments show similarities with segments found among EV drivers, such as cost-conscious drivers, comfort-oriented drivers, pioneers and environmentally conscious drivers in the Netherlands (Duurkoop et al., 2021), or tech-oriented adopters, convenience-oriented adopters, and likely non-adopters of EV product bundles in Switzerland (Plananska & Gamma, 2022).

Looking at the characteristics of the members of the three segments beyond the charging preferences, surprisingly few differences were found (for the detailed data, see Table 4 in the appendix). Regarding the EV purchase decision, segment 1 is closer to an EV purchase, with a higher share of respondents intending to buy an EV within the next two years. Segment 2 has the youngest group members on average, followed by segment 3 which is similar to the overall average, and segment 1 has the highest average age. Segment 3 comes with comparatively lower prior exposure to EVs. Perceived climate knowledge shows an equal distribution across all three segments. Similarly, the segments are very comparable in how respondents estimate EV's contribution to CO₂ emission reduction. Segment 3, the likeliest adopters, does not fall under the typical classification of early adopters of green products. Members of this segment show high but still distributed self-responsibility to fight climate change. When it comes to the speed of the energy transition in Switzerland, this segment shows the comparatively lowest preference for a fast energy transition across the three segments. Segment 3 also shows a fairly wide distribution in income, declining the hypothesis of this being a high-income class.

Fig. 5. Willingness-to-accept values for changes in the levels of the charging offer.

4.3. Willingness to co-create flexibility and application examples

Using willingness-to-accept values, the question, “Which compensation should operators offer to incentivize EV drivers to adopt smart charging?” is answered. A base situation is assumed to represent how most EV drivers are likely to charge their EV: home charging for six hours in standard mode.⁷ Fig. 5 presents what a smart EV charging provider would have to offer as compensation to convince EV drivers to shift alternative charging offers by changing one attribute level at a time.

To convince the EV driver to transition from this assumed standard situation to charging at work or a public charging station requires compensation of 6.45 CHF (charging station at work) resp. 10.36 CHF (public charging station). Taking the estimated charging costs of 4 CHF in the assumed standard situation, not even free charging would incentivize the EV driver to make an effort to switch to charging at work or a public charging station. Altering the charging duration to four or two hours, the EV driver would be willing to pay 6.95 and 3.57 CHF, respectively, since this represents an improvement in the assumed standard situation. To accept a managed charging process with the option that the battery could only be charged 5 % after half of the charging period, EV drivers

Table 3

Scenario analysis of concrete charging situations and required charging tariffs to achieve breakeven.

	Scenario A	Option B1	WTA for B1	Option B2	WTA for B2	Option 3	WTA for B3
Location	Home	Work	-6.45 CHF	Home	0 CHF	Public	-10.36 CHF
Charging Costs	10 CHF						
Charging Duration	6 h	4 h	+3.57 CHF	2 h	+6.95 CHF	2 h	+6.95 CHF
Guaranteed range after 50 % of the charging duration	Standard charging	Eco charging	-4.33 CHF	Eco charging	-4.33 CHF	Eco charging	-4.33 CHF
Net WTA			-7.21 CHF		+2.62 CHF		-7.74 CHF
Breakeven charging tariff			2.79 CHF		12.62 CHF		2.26 CHF

⁷ Up to today, most EV drivers charge their car at home. I assume that their standard charging process takes 6 h to be completed and it is charged at more or less stable capacity without a management of the charging process (neither towards a comfort mode nor the ECO mode). Under these conditions the EV driver extends the range of the EV by 120 km, requiring about 19 kWh. This assumption is estimated based on the average charging efficiency of gained km per kWh, following a comparison of the energy use of different EVs (ADAC. (2022). *Elektroautos im Test: So hoch ist der Stromverbrauch*. <https://www.adac.de/rund-ums-fahrzeug/tests/elektromobilitaet/stromverbrauch-elektroautos-adac-test/>). With the average of 6.3 km/kWh, an expected charging time of 5.2 h results at a charging capacity of 3.7 kW. For the purpose of this choice experiment and to maintain comprehensibility for the respondents and an uniform design this was rounded up to 6 h. At the regular retail electricity rates this costs about 4 CHF (1 kWh costs in average 0.21 CHF in Switzerland).

expect a compensation of 4.33 CHF. On the other hand, if priority charging is provided, ensuring that the battery is already charged at 95 % after half of the charging period would be valued with an additional willingness-to-pay of 1.07 CHF.

The determined WTA values can be used to analyze concrete application situations of smart charging solutions. For this analysis, the perspective of a smart charging provider was adopted. Smart charging providers are likely to ask questions like: “*What bonus/malus have to be implemented to incentivize EV drivers to change from their current standard charging option (A) to option (B)?*”. Table 3 presents three particular scenarios analyzed. As a starting point the same base situation is assumed.

The first scenario looks at shifting to EV charging at work is one application of particular relevance as it could enable solar charging during the day to help avoid evening demand peaks. This strategy is exceptionally efficient, as EV drivers typically charge at home with long charging durations in standard mode and with relatively low charging costs as a point of departure. Table 3 presents the required charging tariff at work for ECO charging. The net WTA for changing from a typical home charging situation to an ECO charging situation is -7.21 CHF. Consequently, a charging tariff of 2.79 CHF for the 120 km range extension would require the average driver to reach a breakeven utility between the concepts.

The second scenario aims to introduce faster but moderated charging options at home. Departing from the same reference situation, the alternative of home charging with only two hours of charging duration for the same range and a moderated charging process with ECO charging is introduced. To shift to a fast-charging option at home that comes in combination with ECO charging, EV drivers are willing to pay a premium of 2.62 CHF. Consequently, compared to the base costs, charging could cost 12.62 CHF to break even. This situation indicates that it would be relatively easy to motivate EV drivers to accept ECO charging when compensated with shorter charging times.

The third scenario investigates the willingness to shift to a moderated charging process at a public charging station. A short charging duration is assumed since public charging stations can often provide higher charging capacities. The shorter charging duration, compared to the base situation, can compensate to a partial extent for the lower attractiveness of the location. Overall, the net WTA in this scenario results to -7.74 CHF, leading to a break-even charging tariff 2.26 CHF. This highlights that when home charging is available attractive incentives have to be provided to make EV drivers change to this option.

5. Conclusion

This study investigated the user acceptance of smart charging solutions. By doing so the call for explicit consumer perspectives on smart EV charging and decentralized flexibility is addressed (Gschwendtner et al., 2021; Sovacool et al., 2017; Sovacool et al., 2018). A choice experiment was conducted with a carefully crafted sample of early and potential adopters of EVs. In concrete situations, the respondents had to choose between different charging options varying across location, duration, costs, and moderation of the EV charging process. The results of this study highlight that current and potential EV drivers are indeed willing to participate in smart charging solutions, contributing to the smooth integration of EVs into the electricity grid and helping to increase the uptake of renewable energies as their primary charging source. EV drivers were willing to accept each of the tested charging models. However, EV drivers require compensation for the increased uncertainty, with low charging levels after half of the charging duration. Standard charging that allows to moderate the charging process would only require a small additional compensation than comfort charging, where the EV drivers enjoy the highest priority. Less attractive charging options can be compensated for by lower charging costs, short charging durations, or a shift to a more favorable location. In addition, a bias for home charging among EV drivers was found. The sweet home bias implies that other charging options at other locations will have to be disproportionately more attractive, so EV drivers choose to switch to these alternatives. While most EV drivers do not precisely aim to smart charge their vehicles and instead are willing to accept when the conditions are sufficiently attractive, this study finds a particular segment of early and potential adopters who actively seek to participate in smart charging options. Respondents in this segment are a particularly interesting group to be targeted first with newly launched smart charging offers.

This study provides relevant policy implications for smart charging providers. The detailed estimation of part-worth utilities for attribute levels and willingness-to-accept values allow a translation of the results directly relevant for the marketing of such smart charging offers. Following the study's results, a segment-specific marketing approach should be adopted. Segment 3, as found in this study, should be targeted first as potential early adopters of smart charging. This segment particularly seeks to adopt smart charging offers, having an otherwise balanced preference structure. Communication highlighting the innovativeness, grid support and contribution to integrate renewable energies of smart charging appears as promising. In later stages, the efforts should be broadened to segment 1 as likely early and late majority. For this segment, in particular the financial benefits of smart charging should be addressed and providers should ensure that offers are cost competitive over traditional charging options. In addition, the insights gained can be used for modeling the business strategies and impact of smart charging solutions, allowing empirically supported modeling of user decisions. Various studies that simulate the effects of EV grid integration treat the consumer adoption of smart charging solutions as exogenous (Sovacool et al., 2017), which leads to overestimating the economic attractiveness of smart charging solutions (Wolinetz et al., 2018). However, using empirical data for business model assessment was found to lead to insights relevant for the launching strategy of new business models (Kubli & Canzi, 2021) and reduce the uncertainty of the model results (Kubli, 2020).

This study is limited to the extent to which it considers issues around pricing, membership, and technical requirements for charging. The design of the choice experiment is tailored to avoid interactions between the attributes, on individual level there may however some interactions remaining. In addition, the trade-off between detail and complexity in designing choice experiments meant that no explicit attribute for the electricity source for EV charging was considered. Future research could address this by considering solar charging solutions specifically and investigating whether EV drivers are willing to pay a premium for driving on solar power. In addition, location specific analysis of the willingness to adopt smart charging may bring further insights into the preference structure of

EV drivers, in particular to drivers that are adverse to changing the charging location. While this study focusses on current and potential early EV adopters, future research should also address the later adoption segments. Lastly, the study could be complemented by the operator's perspective and an analysis of the success conditions needed to launch and sustain smart charging solutions.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The author declares that she has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A

See [Tables 4 and 5](#).

Table 4

Contextual characteristics of the sample and the segments determined in the latent class analysis.

	Full Sample		Segment 1		Segment 2		Segment 3	
	Absolute	in %	Absolute	in %	Absolute	in %	Absolute	in %
<i>Sample/Segment size</i> ¹	202	100 %	112	55.45 %	39	19.31 %	51	25.25 %
EV purchase decision								
EV/PHEV owner	18	9 %	13	12 %	4	10 %	1	2 %
Intending to buy an EV in the next two years as the first or second choice of drivetrain technology	63	31 %	37	33 %	11	28 %	15	29 %
Intending to buy an EV in the next three to five years as the first or second choice of drivetrain technology	121	60 %	62	55 %	24	62 %	35	69 %
Availability of charging stations								
There is at least one private charging station where I live.	30	15 %	14	13 %	6	15 %	10	20 %
There is at least one public charging station within walking distance from my home.	48	24 %	26	23 %	7	18 %	15	29 %
At my workplace, charging stations are available.	29	14 %	19	17 %	3	8 %	7	14 %
I wouldn't know where to charge an EV near where I live and work.	107	53 %	59	53 %	23	59 %	25	49 %
EV experience								
I own an EV.	11	5 %	8	7 %	2	5 %	1	2 %
I know someone who owns an EV.	92	46 %	50	45 %	20	51 %	22	43 %
I was already a passenger in an EV.	83	41 %	45	40 %	15	38 %	23	45 %
I drove an EV myself.	47	23 %	27	24 %	11	28 %	9	18 %
I never sat in an EV.	58	29 %	30	27 %	11	28 %	17	33 %
Place of residence								
City	51	25 %	27	24 %	11	28 %	13	25 %
Agglomeration	68	34 %	38	34 %	14	36 %	16	31 %
Countryside	83	41 %	47	42 %	14	36 %	22	43 %
Do you think EVs clearly help to reduce CO2 emissions?								
Yes	59	29 %	38	34 %	12	31 %	9	18 %
Rather yes	103	51 %	52	46 %	19	49 %	32	63 %

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

	Full Sample		Segment 1		Segment 2		Segment 3	
	Absolute	in %	Absolute	in %	Absolute	in %	Absolute	in %
Rather no	26	13 %	14	13 %	4	10 %	8	16 %
No	9	4 %	4	4 %	3	8 %	2	4 %
I don't know	5	2 %	4	4 %	1	3 %	0	0 %
Where do/would you charge your EV? (indicated shares)								
EVO = EV owner	EVO	EVI	EVO	EVI	EVO	EVI	EVO	EVI
EVI = EV interested								
At home	76 %	60 %	73 %	61 %	100 %	66 %	0 %	53 %
At work	14 %	13 %	17 %	12 %	0 %	13 %	0 %	15 %
At a public charging station	9 %	23 %	11 %	22 %	0 %	18 %	0 %	28 %
How much do you think you know about climate change?								
Little	0	0 %	0	0 %	0	0 %	0	0 %
Rather little	14	7 %	4	4 %	5	13 %	5	10 %
Average	111	55 %	60	54 %	27	69 %	24	47 %
Rather much	68	34 %	42	38 %	5	13 %	21	41 %
Very much	9	4 %	6	5 %	2	5 %	1	2 %
To what extent do you feel personally responsible for contributing to fighting climate change?								
	n = 185		n = 85		n = 30		n = 41	
Not at all	4	2 %	2	2 %	0	0 %	2	4 %
2	16	9 %	2	2 %	1	3 %	1	2 %
3	44	24 %	8	8 %	1	3 %	7	14 %
4	88	48 %	26	25 %	6	17 %	12	24 %
Very much	33	18 %	47	45 %	22	61 %	19	39 %
How do you rate the speed of the energy transitions in Switzerland?								
The energy transition progresses too slowly.	128	63 %	77	69 %	24	62 %	27	53 %
The speed of the energy transition is exactly right.	55	27 %	26	23 %	11	28 %	18	35 %
In the energy transition, Switzerland acts with precipitation.	19	9 %	9	8 %	4	10 %	6	12 %
Income								
Less than 3'000 CHF	1	0 %	1	1 %	0	0 %	0	0 %
Between 3'000 and 4'500 CHF	12	6 %	5	5 %	1	3 %	6	12 %
Between 4'501 and 6'000 CHF	25	12 %	16	17 %	6	15 %	3	6 %
Between 6'001 and 9'000 CHF	51	25 %	29	30 %	10	26 %	12	24 %
Between 9'001 and 12'000 CHF	49	24 %	24	25 %	10	26 %	15	29 %
More than 12'000 CHF	36	18 %	21	22 %	7	18 %	8	16 %
Prefer not to declare	28	14 %	16	17 %	2	0 %	3	0 %
Language								
German	148	73 %	84	75 %	27	69 %	37	73 %
French	54	27 %	28	25 %	12	31 %	14	27 %
Age								
	44.45		46.31					
			42.39					
			44.74					
Gender								
Male	127	63 %	25	64 %	32	63 %	70	63 %
Female	75	37 %	14	36 %	19	37 %	42	38 %

¹ The difference of the segment size in the latent class analysis results and the sample characteristics chart arises from that latent class analysis is based on probability of membership to a segment (Sawtooth, 2021), while the later applies a discrete allocation to one segment.

Table 5

Results overview on the overall sample along the importance values and part-worth utilities and the statistical descriptions.

	Relative importance of attribute	Std. deviation	95 % confidence interval
Location	25.66	11.40	[24.085; 27.23]
Costs	39.11	14.79	[37.075; 1.154]
Duration	16.15	8.38	[14.996; 17.308]
Guaranteed reach after 50 %	19.08	13.24	[17.25; 20.903]
	Part-worth utility	Std. deviation	95% confidence interval
at home	40.68	31.55	[36.33; 45.033]
at work	-6.14	43.89	[-12.188; -0.083]
at a public charging station	-34.55	35.54	[-39.448; -29.646]
0 CHF	77.26	40.95	[71.611; 82.907]
10 CHF	-9.31	18.84	[-11.908; -6.71]
20 CHF	-67.95	41.55	[-73.68; -62.22]
2 h	25.00	25.25	[21.521; 28.485]
4 h	0.46	19.50	[-2.233; 3.146]
6 h	-25.46	23.98	[-28.766; -22.152]
ECO mode 5%	-23.56	42.52	[-29.423; -17.695]
Standard mode 50%	7.88	16.19	[5.645; 10.11]
Comfort mode 95%	15.68	40.84	[10.049; 21.314]
n	202		
Number of observations	1818		
RLH	0.610		

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